

SKOLEM MEAN LABELING OF FOUR STAR AND FIVE STAR GRAPHS

$$K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2} \text{ where } \tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 4$$

$$K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\eta_3} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2} \text{ where } \tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 - \eta_3 \equiv 4$$

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Abstract

A graph $G = (V, E)$ with p vertices and q edges is said to be a skolem mean graph if there exists a function f from the vertex set of G to $\{1, 2, \dots, p\}$ such that the induced map f^* from the edge set of G to $\{2, 3, \dots, p\}$ defined by $f^*(e = uv) = \frac{f(u)+f(v)}{2}$ if $f(u) + f(v)$ is even and $\frac{f(u)+f(v)+1}{2}$ if $f(u) + f(v)$ is odd, then the resulting edges get distinct labels from the set $\{2, 3, \dots, p\}$. The condition for a graph G to be a skolem mean is that $p \geq q+1$. In this paper, we prove that the four star graph $K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2}$ where $\eta_1 \leq \eta_2$ and $\tau_1 \leq \tau_2$ is a skolem mean graph if $\tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 4$ and the five star graph $K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\eta_3} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2}$ where $\eta_1 \leq \eta_2 \leq \eta_3$ and $\tau_1 \leq \tau_2$ is a skolem mean graph if $\tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 - \eta_3 \equiv 4$.

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1. Introduction

Let $G(V, E)$ be a simple, connected graph where $V(G)$ is its vertex set and $E(G)$ is its edge set. In this paper, we prove that four star graph $G = K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2}$ where $\eta_1 \leq \eta_2$ and $\tau_1 \leq \tau_2$ is a skolem mean graph if $\tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 4$ and the five star graph $G = K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\eta_3} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2}$ where $\eta_1 \leq \eta_2 \leq \eta_3$ and $\tau_1 \leq \tau_2$ is a skolem mean graph if $\tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 - \eta_3 = 4$. All graphs in this paper are finite, simple and undirected. Terms not defined here are used in the sense of Harary [1].

Definition 1.1

A vertex labelling of a graph G is an assignment of labels to the vertices of G that induces for each edge xy a label depending on the vertex labels $f(x)$ and $f(y)$. Similarly, an edge labelling of a graph G is an assignment of labels to the edges of G that induces for each vertex v a label depending on the edge labels incident on it. Total labelling involves a function from the vertices and edges to some set of labels.

Definition 1.2: [2]

A graph G with p vertices and q edges is called a mean graph if it is possible to label the vertices $x \in V$ with distinct elements $f(x)$ from $0, 1, 2, \dots, q$ in such a way that when each edge $e = uv$ is labelled with $\frac{f(u)+f(v)}{2}$ if $f(u) + f(v)$ is even and $\frac{f(u)+f(v)+1}{2}$ if $f(u) + f(v)$ is odd, then the resulting edge labels are distinct, f is called a mean labeling of G .

Definition 1.3:[3]

A graph $G = (V, E)$ with p vertices and q edges is said to be a skolem mean graph if there exists a function f from the vertex set of G to $\{1, 2, \dots, p\}$ such that the induced map f^* from the edge set of G to $\{2, 3, \dots, p\}$ defined by $f^*(e = uv) = \frac{f(u)+f(v)}{2}$ if $f(u) + f(v)$ is even and $\frac{f(u)+f(v)+1}{2}$ if $f(u) + f(v)$ is odd, then the resulting edges get distinct labels from the set $\{2, 3, \dots, p\}$

Note 1.4: [3]

The only graphs satisfies the condition $p \geq q + 1$ are paths and stars.

Theorem 1.5: [3]

Any path is a skolem mean graph.

Theorem 1.6: [3]

If $m \geq 4$, $K_{1,m}$ is not a skolem mean graph.

Definition 1.7: [3]

The **union** of n star graphs for $n \geq 2$ is called a **n-star graph**. The general form of n – star graph is $G=K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup \dots \cup K_{1,\eta_n}$ where $\eta_i \geq 1$ for $1 \leq i \leq n$.

2. Main Result

Theorem 2.1

The four star graph $K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2}$ where $\eta_1 \leq \eta_2$ and $\tau_1 \leq \tau_2$ is a skolem mean graph if $\tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 4$.

Proof:

$$\text{Let } N_k = \sum_{i=1}^k \eta_k; 1 \leq k \leq 2; T_k = \sum_{i=1}^k \tau_k; 1 \leq k \leq 2. \text{ That is, } N_1 = \eta_1;$$

$$N_2 = \eta_1 + \eta_2, \text{ and } T_1 = \tau_1; T_2 = \tau_1 + \tau_2.$$

Consider the graph $K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2}$. Let $V = V_1 \cup V_2 \cup V_3 \cup V_4$

be the vertex set of G where $V_k = \{v_{k,i} : 0 \leq i \leq \eta_k\}$ for $1 \leq k \leq 2$ and

$$V_3 = \{v_{3,i} : 0 \leq i \leq \tau_1\}; V_4 = \{v_{4,i} : 0 \leq i \leq \tau_2\}.$$

$$\text{Let } E = \bigcup_{i=1}^2 \{v_{i,0}v_{i,j} : 1 \leq j \leq \eta_i\} \bigcup_{i=1}^2 \{v_{2+i,0}v_{2+i,j} : 1 \leq j \leq \tau_i\} \text{ be the edge set of } G.$$

$$\text{The condition } \tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 = 4 \Rightarrow T_2 = N_2 + 4$$

Let us prove in the above case the graph G is a skolem mean graph.

Case 1:

$$\text{Let } T_2 = N_2 + 4.$$

G has $N_2 + T_2 + 4 = 2N_2 + 8$ vertices and $N_2 + T_2 = 2N_2 + 4$ edges. The vertex labeling $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, N_2 + T_2 + 4 = 2N_3 + 8\}$ is defined as follows:

$$f(v_{1,0}) = 1; \quad f(v_{2,0}) = 3; \quad f(v_{3,0}) = N_2 + T_2 + 1 = 2N_2 + 5;$$

$$f(v_{4,0}) = N_2 + T_2 + 3 = 2N_2 + 7;$$

$$f(v_{1,r}) = 2r + 3 \quad 1 \leq r \leq \eta_1$$

$$f(v_{2,r}) = 2N_1 + 2r + 3 \quad 1 \leq r \leq \eta_2$$

$$f(v_{3,r}) = 2r \quad 1 \leq r \leq \tau_1$$

$$f(v_{4,r}) = 2T_1 + 2r \quad 1 \leq r \leq \tau_2$$

The corresponding edge labels are as follows:

The edge label of $v_{1,0}v_{1,r}$ is $2+r$ for $1 \leq r \leq \eta_1$ (edge labels are $3, 4, \dots, \eta_1 + 2 = N_1 + 2$), $v_{2,0}v_{2,r}$ is $N_1 + 3 + r$ for $1 \leq r \leq \eta_2$ (edge labels are $N_1 + 4, N_1 + 5, \dots, N_1 + \eta_2 + 3 = N_2 + 3$), $v_{3,0}v_{3,r}$ is $N_2 + 3 + r$ for $1 \leq r \leq \tau_1$ (edge labels are $N_2 + 4, N_2 + 5, \dots, N_2 + \tau_1 + 3$), $v_{4,0}v_{4,r}$ is $N_2 + \tau_1 + 4 + r$ for $1 \leq r \leq \tau_2$ (edge labels are $N_2 + \tau_1 + 5, N_2 + \tau_1 + 6, \dots, N_2 + \tau_1 + \tau_2 + 4 = 2N_2 + 8$). These induced edge labels of graph G are distinct. Hence G is a skolem mean graph.

Example:

The following graph $G = K_{1,3} \cup K_{1,4} \cup K_{1,5} \cup K_{1,6}$ is a Skolem mean graph

Figure1: $G = K_{1,3} \cup K_{1,4} \cup K_{1,5} \cup K_{1,6}$

Theorem 2.2

The five star graph $K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\eta_3} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2}$ where $\eta_1 \leq \eta_2 \leq \eta_3$ and $\tau_1 \leq \tau_2$ is a skolem mean graph if $\tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 - \eta_3 \equiv 4$.

Proof:

Let $N_k = \sum_{i=1}^k \eta_i; 1 \leq k \leq 3$; $T_k = \sum_{i=1}^k \tau_i; 1 \leq k \leq 2$ That is $N_1 = \eta_1;$

$N_2 = \eta_1 + \eta_2; N_3 = \eta_1 + \eta_2 + \eta_3,$ and $T_1 = \tau_1; T_2 = \tau_1 + \tau_2.$

Consider the graph $K_{1,\eta_1} \cup K_{1,\eta_2} \cup K_{1,\eta_3} \cup K_{1,\tau_1} \cup K_{1,\tau_2}$

Let $V = V_1 \cup V_2 \cup V_3 \cup V_4 \cup V_5$ be the vertex set of G where

$$V_k = \{v_{k,i} : 0 \leq i \leq \eta_k\} \text{ for } 1 \leq k \leq 3 \text{ and}$$

$$V_4 = \{v_{4,i} : 0 \leq i \leq \tau_1\}; V_5 = \{v_{5,i} : 0 \leq i \leq \tau_2\}.$$

Let $E = \bigcup_{i=1}^3 \{v_{i,0}v_{i,j} : 1 \leq j \leq \eta_i\} \bigcup_{i=1}^2 \{v_{3+i,0}v_{3+i,j} : 1 \leq j \leq \tau_i\}$ be the edge set of G.

The condition $\tau_1 + \tau_2 - \eta_1 - \eta_2 - \eta_3 \equiv 4 \Rightarrow T_2 = N_3 + 4$

Let us prove in the above case the graph G is a skolem mean graph.

Case 1:

Let $T_2 = N_3 + 4.$

G has $N_3 + T_2 + 4 = 2N_3 + 9$ vertices and $N_3 + T_2 = 2N_3 + 4$ edges. The vertex labeling $f : V \rightarrow \{1, 2, 3, \dots, N_3 + T_2 + 5 = 2N_3 + 9\}$ is defined as follows:

$$f(v_{1,0}) = 1; f(v_{2,0}) = 2; f(v_{3,0}) = 4; f(v_{4,0}) = 2N_3 + 6;$$

$$f(v_{5,0}) = N_3 + T_3 + 4 = 2N_3 + 8$$

$$f(v_{1,r}) = 2r + 4 \quad 1 \leq r \leq \eta_1$$

$$f(v_{2,r}) = 2N_1 + 2r + 4 \quad 1 \leq r \leq \eta_2$$

$$f(v_{3,r}) = 2N_2 + 2r + 4 \quad 1 \leq r \leq \eta_3$$

$$f(v_{4,r}) = 2r + 1 \quad 1 \leq r \leq \tau_1$$

$$f(v_{5,r}) = 2T_1 + 2r + 1 \quad 1 \leq r \leq \tau_2$$

The corresponding edge labels are as follows:

The edge label of $V_{1,0}V_{1,r}$ is $3+r$ for $1 \leq r \leq \eta_1$ (edge labels are $4, 5, \dots, \eta_1 + 3 = N_1 + 3$), $v_{2,0}v_{2,r}$ is $N_1 + 3 + r$ for $1 \leq r \leq \eta_2$ (edge labels are $N_1 + 4, N_1 + 5, \dots, N_1 + \eta_2 + 3 = N_2 + 3$), $v_{3,0}v_{3,r}$ is $N_2 + 4 + r$ for $1 \leq r \leq \eta_3$ (edge labels are $N_2 + 5, N_2 + 6, \dots, N_2 + \eta_3 + 4 = N_3 + 4$), $v_{4,0}v_{4,r}$ is $N_3 + 4 + r$ for $1 \leq r \leq \tau_1$ (edge labels are $N_3 + 5, N_3 + 6, \dots, N_3 + \tau_1 + 4$), $v_{5,0}v_{5,r}$ is $N_3 + \tau_1 + 5 + r$ for $1 \leq r \leq \tau_2$ (edge labels are $N_3 + \tau_1 + 6, N_3 + \tau_1 + 7, \dots, N_3 + \tau_1 + 5 + \tau_2 = 2N_3 + 9$)

These induced edge labels of graph G are distinct.

Hence G is a skolem mean graph.

Example: The following graph $G=K_{1,3} \cup K_{1,4} \cup K_{1,5} \cup K_{1,7} \cup K_{1,9}$ is a Skolem mean graph

Figure 2: $G=K_{1,3} \cup K_{1,4} \cup K_{1,5} \cup K_{1,7} \cup K_{1,9}$

References:

- [1] F. Harary, Graph Theory, Addison- Wesley, Reading Mass, (1972).
- [2] S. Somasundaram and Raja Ponraj, Mean Labelings Of Graphs, National Academy Science Letters 26(7), January 2003
- [3] V. Balaji, D. S. T. Ramesh and A. Subramanian, Skolem Mean Labeling, Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences, Vol. 26E No. 2 (2007), 245-248.
- [4] V. Balaji, D. S. T. Ramesh and A. Subramanian, Some Results on Skolem Mean graphs, Bulletin of Pure and Applied Sciences, Vol. 27E No. 1 (2008), 67-74.
- [5] J. A Gallian, A Dynamic Survey of Graph Labeling, The Electronic Journal of Combinatorics, 14 (2016), #DS6.
- [6] D.S.T.Ramesh, S.O.Sopna, I.Gnanaselvi and M.P.Syed Ali Nisaya Skolem Mean Labeling Of Four Star Graphs $K_{1,a_1} \cup K_{1,a_2} \cup K_{1,a_3} \cup K_{1,b}$ where $a_1 + a_2 + a_3 + 2 \leq b \leq a_1 + a_2 + a_3 + 3$, International Journal of Scientific Research Vol.6, Issue 8 (Aug. 2017) PP.190-193.